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A series of cell surface markers that identify the onset of transformation in the blood.

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We describe here a series of cell surface markers that identify the onset of transformation in the human blood. The markers include TMEM164, TMEM212, and TMEM87A. We identified these markers using blood from patients with hematopoietic malignancies: with ALL, AML, and CLL. Development and refinement of the dataset provided here will support detection of hematologic malignancy at the population level with a simple annual blood test.